

**Agroecological Solutions for
Resilient Farming in West Africa**

Deliverable 2.1

**Assessment of Stakeholder Requirements and Baseline Information;
Definition of SMART Indicators**

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Author(s)	Saa Dittoh
Contact	Saa Dittoh (saaditt@uds.edu.gh)
Reviewer	Silvia Gómez Valle – CARTIF (silgom@cartif.es)
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¹ R=Document, report; DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; DEC=website, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER=other

² PU=Public, SEN=Sensitive, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CI=Classified

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

AU	African Union
CSOs	Civil Society Organizations
DDA	District Directorate of Agriculture (Ghana)
DSS	Decision Support System
ECOWAS	Economic Community of West African States
EU	European Union
FGDs	Focus group discussions
GD	Green Deal (of the EU)
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GOs	Governmental organizations
KIIs	Key informant interviews
M & E	Monitoring and Evaluation
MMDAs	Municipal, Metropolitan and District Assemblies
NGOs	Non-governmental organizations
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board
SMART (indicators)	Specific, measurable, attainable, realistic and time-bound
UN	United Nations
WP	Work Package

Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1) provides basic baseline information on eight selected CIRAWA regions (islands/districts/zones/regions) of four West African countries: Cape Verde, Ghana, Senegal and The Gambia. The eight regions have been briefly profiled. The two in Cape Verde are islands, those in Ghana are districts, those in Senegal are agroecological zones and those in The Gambia are regions. The main purpose of D2.1 is to present a summary of farmers' and other stakeholders' engagement activities which were meant to introduce CIRAWA and its intended activities as well as the concept of agroecology to the people. The report (D2.1) is also to present what the farmers and other stakeholders consider as their requirements and needs in relation to food production as well as indicators that can be used to assess envisaged interventions.

Since January 2023, there have been several engagements with various stakeholders, particularly farmers and community members by CIRAWA Partners in all the four countries. Preliminary engagements were in the form of "community entries". Multi Actor Approach, where several different methodologies are employed, have been used to sensitize as many potential actors as possible on the aims, goals and methods of operation of the CIRAWA project. Community visits, durbars, focus group discussion (FGDs), key informant interviews (KIIs) and other means of engagements were used. Over 1,500 farmers and over 500 other stakeholders have been sensitized through the various methods.

With respect to what farmers and other stakeholders in the project areas state as their requirements and needs, most farmers and community members state the following: improvements in soil fertility, water availability for irrigation and water management, appropriate mechanization, access to markets, soil conservation measures, access to production resources especially by women and youth, better housing for livestock and provision of feed all year round, effective and informed technical support, provision of quality local seeds and others. Actions to solve the problem of soil salinity was also stressed as a critical requirement of farmers in Senegal and The Gambia.

Basic indicators that will be used for the assessment of progress and achievements of envisaged interventions based on the information obtained have also been presented. They will be refined ("smartened") as project implementation takes place and there is greater understanding of the project areas and their activities. Also, there is need for flexibility so that indicators can be redefined and even changed in the process of project implementation.

D2.1 sets the tone for all activities that will be undertaken in the project because it links project objectives to those of the people (farmers and other stakeholders) in the 8 intervention areas so that co-creation of innovative technologies can be undertaken in the spirit of the 13 principles of agroecology.

1 EXPECTED IMPACT

Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1) is the first deliverable with information from the 8 chosen islands/districts/zones/regions of the four West African countries of the CIRAWA project. The report starts by profiling some pertinent characteristics of the chosen areas. That information helps readers to form a mental picture of the areas CIRAWA will be working in for about 4 years. The report then goes on to discuss various stakeholder engagements, with pictures. That literally takes everyone to the field and that should be good for those who are yet to see what is in the field in the implementing countries.

Most of the information contained in D2.1 is from the people in communities in the chosen regions. The information, therefore, provides all CIRAWA Partners and others first contact of the views of the people that Partners will be working with. Also, the report contains very valuable information on the requirements and needs of men, women and youth farmers as they relate to food production as well as indicators that can be used to assess envisaged interventions. That to a large extent sets the agenda of many of the activities that should be pursued. What is contained in D2.1, therefore, clearly indicates its importance to everyone involved in CIRAWA and the significant expected impact on everyone: CIRAWA researchers, EU personnel working on CIRAWA, the farmers and other stakeholders, including governmental and non-governmental personnel, policy makers, politicians and several other people.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 The CIRAWA Project

CIRAWA – Agroecological Strategies for Resilient Farming in West Africa is an EU-funded project, which aims to “unlock the potential of agroecology in West Africa by building on existing indigenous and scientific knowledge to improve food and nutrition security, livelihoods and planetary health while tackling climate change and environmental impact of agricultural practices”. CIRAWA is working on innovative agroecological approaches using, among others, the following strategies:

- 1) valorisation of agro-wastes and bio-based fertilizer production;
- 2) production of high-quality seeds;
- 3) saline soil reclamation through phytoremediation; and
- 4) soil fertility, water, and crop management practices.

These strategies are to be deployed in 4 countries in West Africa: Cape Verde, Ghana, Senegal, and The Gambia.

The CIRAWA project (and three similar ones in North, East, and Central Africa) arose out of the EU-AU collaborative efforts in agriculture and the focus of the EU to facilitate a green transition according to its Green Deal (GD) objectives, which define the EU’s climate strategy to reach net zero emissions by 2050. It is also in line with the EU-Africa biodiversity strategy, which seeks to create a circular economy.

2.2 Brief Statements on the West African Countries

Cape Verde

Cape Verde (or the Republic of Cabo Verde) is a Portuguese-speaking African country consisting of 10 islands (and 8 islets) situated in the Atlantic Ocean, about 570 kilometers off the coast of the mainland West Africa. Close neighbours include Senegal, The Gambia, and Guinea Bissau. It lies between latitudes 14 and 18 degrees N and longitudes 22 and 26 degrees W. It has a combined area of 4,033 square kilometers and a population of about half a million people (483,628 according to the 2021 census). Its capital is Praia situated on the island of Santiago.

The CIRAWA project is being carried out in communities in Santo Antao, the third largest island with a population of 36,362 (2021 population census), and a much smaller island, Maio, with a population of 6,296 (2021 census). Santo Antao belongs to the Barlavento (windward) group of islands, while Maio belongs to the Sotavento (leeward) group of islands. Santo Antao is a very mountainous, rocky and relatively wet island with considerable vegetation and forests, while Maio is relatively flat,

sandy, and arid with only about 2% of the land being arable. The city of Porto Novo is the capital of Santo Antao while Vila do Maio is the capital of Maio.

About 65% of the people of Cape Verde live in urban settings and over 90% of the food of the country is imported. Agriculture and fishing contribute less than 10% of the GDP. It is however a leader in the use of renewable energy in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA); about 20% of its energy is from renewable energy sources. It is the headquarters of the ECOWAS Regional Centre for Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency.

Ghana

Ghana is an English-speaking West African country with an area of 239,535 square kilometers and a population of about 34 million (UN 2023 estimate). It is the second most populous country in West Africa (after Nigeria). It lies between latitudes 4.5 and 11 degrees N, and longitudes 1 and 3 W. It is bordered by Burkina Faso to the north, Togo to the East, the Gulf of Guinea (part of the Atlantic Ocean) to the south and Cote D'Ivoire and Burkina Faso to the West.

Ghana is divided into 16 regions and 261 metropolitan, municipal and district assemblies (MMDAs), which are the local administrative and political authorities. The CIRAWA project is being carried out in the Central Gonja and Nabdam districts which are both in the northern savannah ecological zone. The Central Gonja District is in the Savannah Region and has woody savannah forest vegetation. It is sparsely populated, about 19 persons per square kilometer (2021 population census) and has mainly nucleated settlements. Farming is largely carried out in "bush farms". The Nabdam District in the Upper East Region is more thickly populated, with about 211 persons per square kilometer (2021 census) and with over 90% grass vegetation. Its settlements are dispersed, that is, houses are dotted throughout the district, and it is difficult to differentiate one community from another. Farming is carried out largely around the homesteads. Central Gonja District is in the cereal (maize/rice)-tuber (yam)-livestock (small and large ruminants) livelihood zone, while Nabdam District is in the cereal (sorghum/millet)-legumes-livestock (small ruminants/guinea fowls) livelihood zone.

Senegal

Senegal is a French-speaking West African country at the westernmost end of mainland Africa. It has a land area of 196,722 square kilometers and a population of about 18 million persons (2023 census). It consists of 14 regions, which are subdivided into 45 departments. It is bordered by Mauritania to the north, Mali to the east, Guinea, and Guinea-Bissau to the south and the Atlantic Ocean to the west. It almost completely surrounds The Gambia. It lies between latitudes 12 and 17 degrees N and longitudes 11 and 18 degrees W.

The country is Sahelian and over 70% of the population are employed in the agricultural sector and the main crops cultivated include rice, groundnuts, sugarcane and cotton as well as a wide variety of fruits and vegetables (green beans, industrial tomato, cherry tomato, melon, mango and others) which are grown for local and export markets. Gum arabic is also produced and exported.

The country is divided into North, Central and South where the South (the Casamance Region) is south of The Gambia. The CIRAWA project is working in the Central West Zone (in Central Senegal) and the North Zone (in the North). Agricultural production in the Central West Zone is largely rainfed while there is significant irrigated agriculture in the North Zone. It is a “rice and gardening” zone.

The Gambia

The Gambia is an English-speaking country sandwiched between Central Senegal and South Senegal (the Casamance region). It has a land area of 11,295 square kilometers and a population of about 2 million people (1,882,450, according to the 2013 population census). It lies between latitudes 13 and 14 degrees N and longitudes 13 and 17 degrees W. It is less than 50 kilometres wide at its widest point. It is the smallest country in mainland West Africa and is divided into 8 local government areas and 43 districts. Agriculture contributes about 30% to the GDP and employs about 70% of the population. Major agricultural activities include crop and livestock production and fishing. Groundnuts and rice are the main crops cultivated. The CIRAWA project is working in the Central River Region (Kerewan) and the North Bank Region (Kuntaur).

2.3 Activities to be Undertaken and Locations

The specific CIRAWA activities that are expected to be undertaken and the specific locations of the activities are given in Table 1. Actual activities to be carried out will be selected according to the needs of the farmers and the appropriateness of the solutions proposed in the project.

Thus, the starting point of CIRAWA activities (Task 2.1) will be to:

- 1) obtain and clearly define what farmers, community members, and other stakeholders regard as their important requirements and needs concerning food production and related activities in the eight regions, and
- 2) define indicators that may be used to determine the success or otherwise of interventions. Indicators should be as SMART (i.e., specific, measurable, attainable, realistic, and time-bound) as possible, and should cover all the most important intervention domains. These indicators are to be obtained through socio-economic and environmental baseline information using FGDs, KIIs, and household surveys.

The selected practices in each of the countries as given in Table 1 have been informed by what is known in each of the countries through previous research activities and available literature on the areas. Poor soil fertility and general inadequate knowledge of the production of composts are problems in the arid and semi-arid parts of Ghana and Senegal where the chosen CIRAWA regions are located. Also, in all four countries there is need for appropriate soil conservation practices depending on the types of soils and the topography of the areas. Soil salinity is a problem in Senegal (and The Gambia) requiring phytoremediation measures which could include agroforestry measures. Crop and household residues can be used for vermicomposting and bio-fertilizer production, but they can also be used for household energy production. Those are important needs of rural people, especially rural women. High quality seed production, appropriate irrigation methodologies, the use of ICT in knowledge sharing and other interventions are all the activities envisaged to be carried out in the various regions of the four countries.

Table 1: Use cases in selected areas in the West African countries.

Activity	Country	Island/Zones/Districts	
Characterisation of local soils: fertility studies	All countries ³	All selected areas	
	Ghana	Central Gonja District	Nabdam District
Characterisation of locally available manures and crop-residues, protocol definition and implementation and production of innovative vermicompost and bio-based fertilisers	Senegal	Central West Zone	North Zone
	Ghana	Central Gonja District	Nabdam District
Characterisation of locally available crop residues and production of materials for household energy production.	The Gambia	Central River Region	North Bank Region
	Cape Verde	Santo Antao	Maio
Soil conservation practices	Ghana	Central Gonja District	Nabdam District
	Senegal	-	North Zone
	The Gambia	Central River Region	North Bank Region
Saline soil reclamation strategies through an integrated approach based on salt-tolerant species (phytoremediation)	Senegal	Central West Zone	North Zone
Crop management decision support system: irrigation, and fertilisation modules	Cape Verde	Santo Antao	Maio
	Ghana	Central Gonja District	Nabdam District
	Senegal	Central West Zone	North Zone
	The Gambia	Central River Region	North Bank Region
High- quality seed production and multiplication	Cape Verde	Santo Antao	Maio
	The Gambia	Central River Region	North Bank Region

³ Even though the proposal indicated that the activity will be for Ghana and Senegal, it was found necessary to include all countries given the critical importance of soil fertility in the project, and the requirements stated by the farmers in all the countries.

Water collection techniques: cloud/fog harvesting	Cape Verde	Santo Antao	Maio
Strategies to increase access of farmers to markets	All countries	All selected areas	
Awareness creation campaigns to promote agro-ecological farming system	All countries	All selected areas	
Farming system cross-border best-practices integration platform	All countries	All selected areas	

3 GENERAL METHODOLOGY

Task 2.1 of the project aimed at identifying relevant stakeholders in the eight chosen regions that can influence (both positively and negatively) project outcomes, and undertaking stakeholder analyses using a multi-actor approach (MAA). That involved several stakeholders, including different types of men and women farmers, mainly smallholder farmers, chiefs and other community leaders, agricultural officers, extension personnel, personnel of non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and civil society organizations (CSOs) operating in the areas, researchers, policy makers, political leaders at different levels of governance and others.

The engagements which were done in several different ways were to:

- 1) sensitize the people on the CIRAWA project and the importance of agroecology and how it resonates with what they already know and are practicing;
- 2) define, with farmers and community members, their requirements and needs with regard to agroecological practices;
- 3) determine, with farmers and community members and other stakeholders, SMART indicators that will be used to measure and evaluate the impact of the project actions for farmers, smallholders and general actors, authorities, etc.

The several methods used for the engagement with stakeholders included well organized “community entries” in the form of visits to Chiefs, opinion leaders and elders, local level political leaders and policy makers and others. There were also formal inaugurations of the project in some of the regions. Focus group discussions (FGDs), key informant interviews (KIIs) and household interviews of men and women were also carried out as part of the socio-economic and environmental assessment of agricultural and livelihood activities of the people in the different regions.

Table 2 gives the numbers of FGDs, KIIs and household interviews that were undertaken in the various regions of the four countries.

Table 2: Numbers of FGDs, KIIs and household interviews that were undertaken.

Country	Island/District/ Region	Number of FGDs (adults)	Number of FGDs (youth)	Number of KIIs	Household interviews	
					Men	Women
Cape Verde	Santo Antao	4		5	26	17
	Maio	3		4	15	0
	Total	7		9	41	17
Ghana	Central Gonja District	10	5	5	25	25
	Nabdam District	9	5	5	25	25
	Total	19	10	10	50	50
Senegal	Central West Zone	10	5	10	15	15
	North Zone	10	10	20	35	35
	Total	20	15	30	50	50
The Gambia	Central River Region North North Bank Region	10	5	10	25	25
	Total	20	10	31	50	50

4 STAKEHOLDER AND OTHER ENGAGEMENTS

4.1 Objectives

Stakeholder engagements were aimed at appropriate “community entry” and introduction of the objectives and modalities of CIRAWA to at least 1000 farmers and 200 other stakeholders and to get acquainted with the people’s objectives and requirements and how they can collaborate in the project.

4.2. Methodology

These activities involved several visits to the different communities to interact with Chiefs, opinion leaders and elders, local level political leaders and policy makers and others as well as the formal inaugurations of the project.

4.3 Results

The several meetings held in the different countries and the numbers of farmers and other stakeholders contacted are as discussed for each country below. In all, about 20 meetings involving over 1,500 men and women farmers and over 500 other stakeholders were engaged.

Cape Verde

CIRAWA has three local partners in Cape Verde, the Ministry of Agriculture and Environment (MAA - Ministerio da Agricultura e Ambiente articulates), the Association of Women of the Eastern Plateau (AMUPAL - Associacao das Mulheres do Planalto Leste) and Association of Young Farmers of the Peri-Urban Area of Porto Novo (AJA or AJAZPUPN - Associacao dos Jovens Agricultores da Zona Peri-Urbana de Porto Novo) as well as ADPM (Associacao de Defesa do Patrimonio Natural e Cultural do Concelho de Mertola), which is based in Portugal but works extensively in Cape Verde. ADPM organized two meetings within the first two weeks of March 2023 in Santo Antao with MAA in which the Minister and some of his staff attended. The second meeting was with the other two local partners AMUPAL and AJA. The objectives and working modalities of the CIRAWA project were discussed with the partners and their associated stakeholders. The main aim was to solicit the active involvement of all key stakeholders in the CIRAWA project. Over 50 persons were involved in these initial meetings. Preliminary visits were also made to Maio between 24th and 28th April 2023 by personnel of ADPM to meet with local stakeholders and to visit farms and learn about farming activities on the island. Over 30 persons took part in the meetings.

Preliminary CIRAWA meeting in Santo Antao

Ghana

In Ghana, the preliminary engagements in early March 2023 involved visits by the two CIRAWA partners, WACWISA-UDS and FIDEP Foundation to the paramount chiefs of the chosen districts of the CIRAWA project. Engagements were undertaken with: 1) the paramount chiefs and elders of the Yapei traditional area in the Central Gonja District of the Savannah Region, 2) the chiefs and elders of Nangodi and Sekoti traditional areas in the Nabdam District of the Upper East Region, 3) the District Chief Executive of Nabdam and her staff who are the local political leaders at the district level, and 4) the District Director of Agriculture (DDA) of Nabdam. The aim of all the engagements was to introduce the CIRAWA project to these key stakeholders and obtain their buy-in. Over 150 people participated in all these engagements.

Senegal

Senegal has one CIRAWA partner, L'Institut Sénégalais de Recherches Agricoles (ISRA). ISRA organised a local workshop from 1 to 3 March 2023, to introduce the project and to explain the importance of the project to key local stakeholders. The meeting was held at ISRA, Saint Louis, and was attended by stakeholders from several governmental and non-governmental agricultural and environmental institutions and organizations as well as farmer groups. Personnel of other agricultural and environmental organizations operating in the chosen study areas also took part in the workshop. About 60 persons attended the workshop.

The Gambia

The Gambia started with one CIRAWA partner, the National Seed Service (NSS). Personnel of the NSS and others (from the Ministry of Agriculture and Research) in March 2023 visited several communities in the Central River Region North and the North Bank Region to introduce the CIRAWA project to opinion leaders. Community fora were held in several communities. Over 50 men and women from the areas were involved in these engagements. Also in April 2023, visits were again made to the two chosen regions to sensitize the people and to prepare them towards the baseline survey which was being planned. Community leaders and the people needed to understand the

reasons for the baseline survey and to give their consent. Again over 50 people were involved in these sensitization engagements.

Ghana CIRAWA preliminary engagement with key stakeholders (Yapei)

Senegal CIRAWA kick-off workshop (Saint Louis)

Formal Inaugurations of the Project

Formal inaugurations of the CIRAWA project took place at different times in the four West African countries. CARTIF, the project coordinating organization took part in the inaugurations. That was necessary to emphasize the international nature of the project and for the people to know that agroecology has worldwide acceptance. The inaugurations took the form of a national forum in Cape Verde, community fora in Ghana and The Gambia, and workshop or conference in Senegal. The total number of people who attended these inaugurations in all the countries is estimated to be over 1000.

A Community forum in May 2023 at the The Gambia

Picture with Paramount Chief after inauguration; CIRAWA inauguration in Central Gonja District,

Ghana

Other Engagements

All the four West African countries of the CIRAWA project have put in place their Stakeholder Advisory Boards (SABs). All have had their first meetings and others have had other meetings. Their suggestions so far have been useful to the country teams.

Some of the countries have also undertaken other stakeholder engagements to sensitize people of different works of life on the work of CIRAWA to give it some visibility; and to keep emphasizing the importance of agroecology. The Ghana CIRAWA team have, for example, held a session during the conference of the Ghana Association of Agricultural Economists (GAAE) on the “the practicability of the 13 principles of agroecology” and also had an opportunity to give a keynote address at an Annual Festival of the Chiefs and people of one of the CIRAWA districts, the Nabdam District.

CIRAWA at GAAE Conference, Ghana

CIRAWA at Annual Tenglegbre Festival of Chiefs and people of Sekoti, Nabdam District

4.4 Conclusion

Over 1,500 farmers and over 500 other stakeholders were engaged in various discussions on the CIRAWA project in the eight selected regions in the four West African countries between March and November 2023. Very good rapport has been established with the various stakeholders in all the countries and the stakeholders have expressed great interest in agroecology and in the CIRAWA project. Many are excited about the project because it resonates well with their interests and their livelihood objectives.

5 FARMERS' REQUIREMENTS AND NEEDS

5.1 Objective

What farmers and other stakeholders regard as their requirements and needs are very pertinent to what decisions are made with regards to envisaged agroecological technologies that will be deployed or introduced to them. The objective here is to identify and clearly define farmers' and other stakeholders' requirements and needs in the different regions. Appropriate interventions can only be designed and adapted to the different areas if the main requirements of farmers and situations under which they operate are known and understood.

5.2 Methodology

Multi-actor approach involves obtaining information from different stakeholders in different ways for effective triangulation and cross-checking of information. Apart from the engagement with stakeholders already discussed, deeper engagement with farmers, agriculture personnel in governmental and non-governmental organizations, opinion leaders and others took place through the FGDs, KIIs, in-depth household surveys and field observations. Both men and women were involved in all the interviews and engagements. The in-depth household surveys involved almost equal numbers of men and women (see Table 2).

Data collection protocols were designed and used to ask for information from farmers and other stakeholders on farmers' requirements and needs as part of the socio-economic and environmental baseline survey. It involved the use of enumerators and supervisors who are conversant with the different environments and the languages spoken by the people. They, however, had to be trained in the data collection process so that they could interact effectively to tease out the important requirements and needs of farmers and community members. WACWISA-UDS team together with other CIRAWA Partners at the country level trained the supervisors and enumerators and took part in some of the field activities. Below are pictures of WACWISA-UDS, Tamale, Ghana baseline survey teams with Partners at supervisors' and enumerators' training sessions in Senegal, The Gambia and Cape Verde.

Senegal

The Gambia

Cape Verde

5.3 Results

The several different farmers' requirements and needs enumerated by the stakeholders in the different countries are as stated for each country below. Several of the requirements and needs are similar across the countries. There are, however, differences in emphasis by the people as to which requirements are most urgent in the different locations.

It should be noted that the information from FGDs and KIIs (see Table 2 above) which are the basis for the discussion in this section is basically qualitative. There is no stratified quantitative data from the FGDs and KIIs. Gendered quantitative information, which is mainly derived from the household interviews of men and women, is presented in Deliverable 2.2 (for Task 2.2). It should also be noted that the specific needs and requirements of women and youth farmers (see Table 3b below) are closely related because of the nature of access to, and inheritance of land and other resources. Land and other resources, such as cattle, are often inherited by the most senior man (such as a brother, paternal uncle or even a paternal cousin) in a family or clan and not a wife, daughter or son, unless the son is the most senior man at the time of the death of a family or clan head.

Cape Verde

a) Access to water:

Due to climatic conditions, one of the primary needs of farmers on the islands is the availability of water for farming and raising livestock. The shortage of water for production has been exacerbated by the lack of rainfall on the islands, leading to the abandonment of some agricultural land. Only about 2% of the land of Maio is arable because of the challenge of the lack of water. Farmers said irrigation was practiced in the past but because water is now very limited, they cannot do so now. Farmers are requesting that drip irrigation techniques could be the solution since the techniques ensure minimal use of water. Water storage facilities can be used to store rainwater during the rainy season for irrigation in the dry season. A part of the Maio (Figueira), however, has much more water and irrigated agriculture is commonly practiced. Lack of water for irrigation is also a problem in some parts of the Santo Antao Island, even though in several parts (e.g. Alto Mira, Casa do Meio and

Ribeira da Cruz⁴), irrigated agriculture is commonly practiced. The major requirement in those areas is drip irrigation facilities so that water can be conserved. Water storage facilities (to be used for irrigation) are also important requirements of the farmers on both islands.

b) A large forest plantation of a single tree type in Maio (complete lack of biodiversity)

A key informant from Maio thinks the forest plantation (of a single tree type covering a large portion of the island) is a major problem and there is a need to do something about it. Another key informant believes the tree, an acacia plant, is the cause of the drying up of most parts of the Maio land. He says the island was good agricultural land prior to the establishment of that forest plantation. These comments and thoughts of the informants are just assumptions based on their opinions, so further interrogation is required. It would have been good to obtain more opinions of different people including different gender. However, it was difficult to get more key informants in Maio, and it was almost impossible to have access to women to talk to them, either in FGDs or to interview them individually. It is a cultural issue that can be overcome with several visits and longer periods of interaction with the people.

c) Transportation of agricultural products

Better and appropriate means of transport are required to send agricultural products, especially fruits and vegetables, to markets. The poor transport situation results in significant loss of the produce physically and in value terms. Donkeys are used in some parts of the islands for transporting agricultural produce. This requirement is particularly acute for women since marketing of agricultural products tend to be more of women's activities.

d) Lack of labor and equipment

There is significant shortage of farm labour in the production seasons mainly due to rural-urban migration and the ageing of the farming population. A possible solution is appropriate agricultural intensification methods. Appropriate agroecological practices are part of their needs and requests.

e) Lack of finance

According to the farmers, finance to purchase agricultural inputs such as quality seeds, fertilizers, basic agricultural tools, irrigation equipment and personal protective equipment is one of their main requirements and needs.

f) Technical support and assistance:

Farmers, especially in Maio, say they have limited agricultural extension support. They do not have adequate access to available technical knowledge to improve food production.

⁴ It is good to know that 80% of the irrigated system in Ribeira da Cruz is drip irrigation.

g) Control of agricultural pests and diseases:

Again, mainly in Maio, locust infestation is very common. There is also the problem of the presence of the hen of the woods (*Numida meleagris*), which invades the agricultural fields during periods of high production. In Santo Antão, the millipede *Bandeirenica caboverda*, locally known as “mil-pés” is one of the main causes of tuber crop losses among farmers.

h) Need to restore local seeds

A key informant from Santo Antao thinks the loss of local corn (maize) and bean seeds is a problem and there is a need to find ways of restoring local seeds that are more adapted to the environment.

i) Training and empowerment:

The farmers also believe they need assistance to organize themselves into farmer groups so that they can benefit from cooperative activities, and also be part of networks of producers and consumers to benefit from fair prices of inputs and their output.

j) Livestock Management Skills and Resources:

Informants and stakeholder advisors from Santo Antão reflected on the impact of extensive livestock rearing practices in increasingly arid and unvegetated areas of both Santo Antão and Maio islands. They concluded that action is needed to educate livestock farmers on rotational grazing, pasture improvement, fodder cultivation and animal confinement, in order to reduce the impacts of herds on local soils and ecosystems in general.

Ghana**a) Poor soil fertility**

Degraded soil has been identified by farmers in both the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts as major problems that need to be addressed. According to the farmers, farm productivity has been declining over the years and the use of fertilizers has not helped much. According to some of the farmers, they are in a “fertilizer trap”, where fertilizers are not helping much, and they cannot stop using them for lack of an alternative. According to a key informant, “fertilizers must be used on the high-yielding varieties of maize and rice and yet the fertilizer is destroying the soil”. They are aware of the existence of organic soil amendments, but they have no access to any. Compost making is a technique they are willing to improve upon. The requirement for soil fertility improvements is more acute for women farmers particularly in the Nabdam District mainly because lands that men allocate to the women are less fertile. Agricultural lands are largely inherited, and women do not inherit land from their parents.

b) Market access for agricultural produce

A major identified need of farmers is a market for their produce. Roots and tubers (such as yam in the Central Gonja District) and vegetables (in both districts) which are highly perishable suffer from limited access to markets at harvest time. They claim poor access to markets for all types of agricultural produce is a problem in most parts of Ghana. The problem is more acute for women because they are more into the marketing of agricultural product, especially grains, vegetables and fruits.

c) Irregular rainfall and floods

Farmers mentioned measures against irregular rainfall and persistent floods during the rainy season as some of their needs. They do not know what can be done by anybody but those are their problems that need solutions.

d) Limited access to irrigation

The Central Gonja District is drained by the White and Black Volta rivers and their tributaries so there is abundant surface water for irrigated agriculture. Also, the Nabdam District has considerable groundwater which can be harnessed for irrigation. In both cases, farmers referred to constraints of resources, equipment and knowledge. Pumps and drip irrigation facilities are their requirements for irrigated agriculture.

e) Appropriate tools for weed control in farms

The farmers, especially women, noted that they are forced to use herbicides to control weeds, even though they know the high health risks, because of the lack of appropriate tools for land preparation and control of weeds. How to stop the use of herbicides and other synthetic agrochemicals in farming is a critical need of the farmers.

f) Access to farm inputs

Poor access to, and high prices of farm inputs such as improved seeds, fertilizers etc. especially by those in remote areas have been problems for a long time. What should be done to provide the inputs at reasonable prices is a major need.

g) Limited finance resources to invest in farms

Access to financial resources for farming is almost non-existent in most farming communities in the districts. The farmers say they cannot adopt any better farm practices without financial support to obtain the required inputs and equipment.

h) Management of livestock (housing, feed, water, veterinary services)

A major need of men and women farmers in the Central Gonja and Nabdam Districts of Ghana is better management of their livestock (poultry, small ruminants, pigs, and cattle).

i) Destruction of farms by wildlife (elephants)

A major problem of Nabdam District farmers is the destruction of their farms by wildlife, particularly elephants. They believe the Government can take appropriate measures to solve that problem.

j) Access to agricultural land by women and youth

Unique needs for many women and youth, particularly in the Nabdam District of Ghana, are access to farmland and ways of more intensive use of the limited land available to them. The Nabdam District is thickly populated (about 211 people per square kilometer - 2021 census), and under such a situation woman and the youth very low access to farmland.

Senegal**a) Degraded soils**

Farmers in the chosen zones of Senegal believe the farmlands are very degraded because of continuous cultivation of the land, increasing salinity of the soil and the use of chemical fertilizers. That means their main needs are how to solve those problems. Production of bio-fertilizers, including compost, is a major requirement of Senegalese farmers.

b) Poor rainfall and poor access to irrigation opportunities

Senegal is in the Sahel region thus low and erratic rainfall has been the case over time. However, farmers believe climate change is worsening the situation and so they require knowledge that can help them contribute to tackling the climate change problem. Also, they require greater access to irrigation facilities and opportunities. The North Zone is a major irrigation area. Large community irrigation schemes developed by the government are used for rice and diversification crops. Alongside these community perimeters, there are many small farms growing market garden crops. This is the case, for example, in the Lac de Guiers area, where farmers use motor-driven pumps and earth pipes to irrigate their plots. There are also large private farms growing sugar cane and horticultural crops. The women specifically say their greatest requirements are water pumps and drip irrigation facilities to facilitate their irrigation activities. They also need boots and gloves to prevent water-borne diseases. Irrigation in the Central West Zone is rudimentary. It is limited to small vegetable gardens. Thus, a major requirement in that zone are irrigation infrastructures and opportunities for women and the youth to undertake irrigated agriculture.

c) Poor access to markets, especially for irrigated produce

Access to markets and appropriate transportation facilities (for the produce) are also major requirements of irrigators in the North Zone in particular, where irrigated agriculture is relatively advanced.

d) Limited access to land by women and the youth

Women and youth farmers in the Central West Zone of Senegal have very limited access to land. The limited land used by women are mainly inherited from their mothers and are small areas. The land issue is quite complex. “Family farming” on family lands is the normal practice so in the case of limited land, individuals find it difficult to have their own land for farming.

e) Livestock feed (fodder)

Livestock is a major livelihood activity in Senegal but there have been constraints to providing adequate feed to the livestock during the dry season. Thus, a major need of farmers and community members is a sustainable way to obtain livestock feed all year round. Good crop-livestock integration techniques can be useful but they have very limited knowledge of how that works.

f) Poultry problems – Heat and diseases

The main requirement with respect to poultry (chicken) production in Senegal is how to reduce the heat that affects chicks during hot periods as well as some poultry diseases.

The Gambia**a) Poor soil fertility, poor access to fertilizer and high cost of fertilizers**

Improvements in soils is the major requirement of farmers in The Gambia. They say the fertility of soils is very low and chemical fertilizers are not easily accessible and very expensive. Organic fertilizers are also required but they are also inaccessible. Good composting methods are required.

b) Quality seeds

Inadequate quality seeds have also been listed as a main constraint in their food production. They believe poor quality seeds as well as poor soil fertility are the cause of low yields and low incomes. So, a major requirement is the availability of high-quality seeds for their staple crops: rice, maize, groundnuts and others.

c) Limited access to markets and storage facilities, and high transport costs

Farmers in The Gambia say they have limited access to markets for farm produce and to appropriate storage facilities, and the cost of transportation of farm produce to urban centres is prohibitive. This

is particularly serious in the case of perishable crops such as fruits and vegetables. Easier access to markets is a particularly acute requirement for women in The Gambia.

d) Insufficient arable land

The available land for agricultural purposes, especially in the Central River Region North, is very limited. A major requirement is how to get the most output from very limited land. As in all the other countries this is a more acute problem for women and the youth.

e) Soil salinity

Soil salinity is a problem in the North Bank Region and how to solve the problem is a major need of farmers in the area.

f) Pests and disease in vegetable production

There are various pests and diseases that attack vegetables and solutions are yet to be found. How to tackle those problems are stated requirements and needs of farmers.

g) Poor housing for small ruminants and poor access to grazing lands

While the Central River Region North farmers regard better housing for their small ruminants as their major requirement, the North Bank Region farmers' main requirement with respect to livestock is access to grazing lands. Appropriate livestock housing and sustainable feeding systems for livestock are major requirements of farmers in The Gambia, and it is likely the same in the other West African countries.

h) Erratic rainfall and lack of irrigation infrastructure

The Gambia, just like Senegal, is a Sahel country and thus low and erratic rainfall seems normal. It has, however, been getting worse over the last decade and some actions should be taken. They will be happy to be part of actions that can be taken. One action they believe is important is irrigated agriculture. Better irrigated infrastructure and knowledge are the farmers' requirements regarding irrigation. Pumps and drip irrigation facilities have been stated as important to them.

i) Lack of access to production resources by women and youth

Access to rainfed and irrigated lands, farm equipment, quality seeds, fertilizers, credit facilities and others, are constraints almost all the farmers (men and women) face in The Gambia. They are, however, acute for women and youth. Women and youth can, for example, access farm implements for their farms only after household heads (who are mainly men) use them on the family farms and their own individual farms. Late access to farm implements will imply late planting resulting in poor harvests. Thus, the major requirements of women and youth are better access to agricultural production resources.

j) Inadequate technical know-how

Farmers in The Gambia believe they do not have adequate technical know-how to increase agricultural productivity and require assistance from agricultural scientists and others.

k) Wildlife intrusion

Wildlife has from time to time entered and destroyed farmlands. How to keep them away from farms is a requirement of farmers.

5.4 Conclusions

Even though few significant differences can be noted between the different regions, many farmers' and communities' requirements are similar across the countries. They include the need for improvements in soil fertility, water availability and management, appropriate mechanization, access to markets, soil conservation measures, better housing for livestock and provision of feed all year round, access to production resources by women and youth and others. Actions to solve the problem of soil salinity was also stressed as a critical requirement of farmers in Senegal and The Gambia (see Table 3).

Table 3: Summary table of farmers' requirements and needs in the four countries.

Major farmers' and communities' requirements and needs	Countries in which requirements were stated			
	CV	Ghana	Senegal	Gambia
1. Soil fertility improvements (with emphasis on composting, implying agro-waste valorization and bio-fertilizer production).	✓	✓	✓	✓
2. Access to water for agriculture (irrigation)/Access to irrigation opportunities and equipment.	✓ (esp. in Maio)	✓	✓	✓
3. Marketing of produce (including transportation).	✓	✓	✓	✓
4. Limited farm labour and therefore provision of appropriate farm equipment/mechanization.	✓	✓	✓	✓
5. Financial provision to farmers and small scale entrepreneurs (processors, traders etc.).	✓	✓	-	✓
6. Technical support and assistance/Training and empowerment.	✓	-	✓	✓
7. Restoration of local seeds.	✓	-	-	-
8. Access to high yielding crop varieties and other farm inputs.	-	✓	✓	✓

9. Soil conservation measures for water management (including water retention/storage and flood control).	✓	✓	✓	✓
10. Improvements in the management of livestock (housing, feed, water etc.).	✓	✓	✓	✓
11. Measures to control menace of wildlife.	-	✓	-	✓
12. Access to land and other production resources by women and youth.	-	✓	✓	✓
13. Insufficient arable land, so need for methods of appropriate and affordable sustainable agricultural intensification (SAI).	-	-	-	✓
14. Methods to solve the problem of soil salinity.	-	-	✓	✓
15. Appropriate measures to controls pests and diseases especially in vegetable production.	✓	-	✓	✓

Table 3b: Summary table of requirements and needs unique and/or more acute to women and youth⁵ in the four countries.

Requirements and needs unique and/or acute to women and youth	Cape Verde	Ghana	Senegal	The Gambia
1) Access to farmlands (land inheritance leaves out women and land too limited to be allocated to youth). Main solution is intensification (SAI)	✓ (Santo Antao)	✓ (esp. in Nabdam)	✓ (esp. in Central West Zone)	✓
2) Availability of organic soil amendments (for women in particular)	✓	✓ (esp. in Nabdam)	-	✓
3) Marketing of farm produce (including transportation), especially fruits and vegetables	✓	✓	✓ (esp. in North Zone)	✓
4) Farm labour (particularly by women farmers)	✓	✓	-	-
5) Access to other production inputs (seed, fertilizers etc)	-	-	-	✓

⁵ As explained in Section 5.3, the main specific needs and requirements of women and youth farmers are very similar because of the nature of inheritance and access to land for farming in most West African farming communities.

6 DEFINITION OF (SMART) INDICATORS

6.1 Objective

The requirements and needs of farmers and other stakeholders from the eight CIRAWA project areas have been identified. It is necessary to also identify a set of indicators that can be used to monitor and evaluate the extent to which these requirements and needs are being met or tackled by the interventions to be employed. The objective of this section is to define such indicators. The start of monitoring and evaluation (M & E) process at project inception is important so that activities can be systematically assessed, and necessary changes made at appropriate stages. This is particularly important in an agroecological project such as CIRAWA where co-creation, co-innovation and co-adaptation of technologies and interventions are essential components of the process.

6.2 Methodology

The extensive engagement of farmers and the other stakeholders has resulted in a significant mass of information, and with information from gray literature, relevant indicators have been teased out. It is important to note that there are different types of indicators (input, output, outcome, process, and impact indicators) depending on the types of farmers' requirements and needs identified. Indicators generally indicate the presence, absence and/or level of a concept, condition and/or situation. Thus, based on known or perceived situations and/or conditions the indicators have been derived. Their level of « SMARTness » depend on the level of detail of information available on the stated requirements and needs.

6.3 Results

Table 4 gives the indicators for the various identified requirements and needs of farmers and other stakeholders. Since FGDs, KIIs, and other qualitative engagements with stakeholders as well as review of gray literature are the sources of information for the definition of the indicators many of them (the indicators) may not be as “smart” as would have been. Some of them will be “smartened” with results from activities of the different Work Packages as they are implemented. Thus, there will be revisions of the indicators to make them “smarter” and for changes, if there is a need to do so. It is, for example, likely that competitive effects of livestock, crop and forestry interventions, negative externalities, synergies of interventions and other situations will occur, but it is difficult to estimate now the degree of these interactive effects. The revision and refinement of the indicators will consider most of these as more information is obtained through increased interaction with farmers and other stakeholders in the communities and the countries. Some of these situations are already being seen in Task 2.2 (and D2.2). Information in D2.2 and D2.3 as well as data being collected for D3.1 and D3.7 will be used for the refinement of the indicators.

Table 4 : Definition of SMART indicators

Major farmers' and communities' requirements and needs		Definition of relevant SMART indicators (To be "smartened" with results from intervention activities)	Targets
1.	Soil fertility improvements	Fertility improvements (measured in terms of organic matter content and quality).	Increase fertility (nutrients) and/or organic matter by 20% by July 2026.
2.	Access to water for agriculture (irrigation)/Access to irrigation opportunities and equipment	Water use efficiency measures.	Increase 15% water use efficiency by December 2026.
3.	Marketing of produce (including transportation)	Improve the access to the markets and incomes of diversification through the development of sustainable products supported by trainings in business plan and market strategies.	30% of the attendees to the dissemination activities receive course on business plans and market strategies by December 2025.
4.	Limited farm labour and therefore provision of appropriate farm equipment/mechanization.	Link with relevant stakeholders (GOs and NGOs) to work on appropriate mechanization for agroecological technologies.	- (Difficult to put a target since actions depend more on persons not under the control of the project)
5.	Financial provision to farmers and small-scale entrepreneurs (processors, traders etc.)	Creation of new market opportunities (business plan and marketing strategies trainings) and promote the agroecological governance (by policy dialogues and community meetings with regional officials, policy maker and relevant local leaders).	At least 6 policy dialogues and 6 community meetings undertaken and at least 2 business cases proposed per country by December 2026.
6.	Technical support and assistance/Training and empowerment	Trainings and workshops on agroecology, agroforestry and other agroecological practices.	At least 1,300 farmers trained in 54 workshops and specific training sessions by December 2026
7.	Restoration of local seeds	Production and multiplication of indigenous high-quality seeds.	At least two different local seeds produced in Cape Verde and The Gambia by June 2027.
8.	Access to high yielding crop varieties and other farm inputs	i) Access to quality staple crops and vegetable seeds.	i) At least 30 farms in each country access quality seeds by June 2026.

		ii) Reduction of production costs and prices of agricultural inputs.	ii) At least 5% reduction in production cost by June 2026.
9.	Soil conservation measures for water management (including water retention/storage and flood control)	i) Adoption of soil conservation and water management practices. ii) Use of water harvesting techniques.	-
10.	Improvements in the management of livestock (housing, feed, water etc.)	Attendees to livestock management training programmes.	-
11.	Measures to control menace of wildlife	Relevant agencies sensitized on the need for control measures against the menace of wildlife in the areas affected.	-
12.	Access to land and other production resources by women and youth	Dialogue fora on land access by women and youth held with Chiefs and landowners.	-
13.	Insufficient arable land, so need for methods of appropriate and affordable sustainable agricultural intensification (SAI)	Agroecological technologies are appropriate SAI technologies. Use of combined agroecological strategies and techniques.	At least 100 farms adopting combined strategies by June 2025
14.	Methods to solve the problem of soil salinity	i) Adoption of soil restoration practices (phytoremediation, composting etc.) ii) Salt tolerant crop varieties introduced	Soil restoration practices undertaken in at least 25% of affected farms in the regions of Senegal and The Gambia by June 2026.
15.	Appropriate measures to controls pests and diseases especially in vegetable production.	Adoption of integrated pest management (IPM) practices.	-

The targets presented in Table 4 have been extracted from the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA) and are designed to reflect the project's objectives, particularly in addressing the needs of farmers. Additionally, Deliverable 2.3 provides an updated and refined selection of KPIs that are more closely aligned with the project's goals. Within this deliverable, certain parameters have already been defined to start working on the process of making these indicators "SMART" (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound). Furthermore, before the implementation phase and the initiation of monitoring activities, these indicators will undergo an in depth and meticulous review. This additional step will ensure that all necessary parameters are fully defined and optimized, allowing the indicators to be completely SMART and ready to effectively guide and measure the project's progress toward achieving its goals.

6.4 Conclusion

SMART indicators to be used for the purpose of assessing the progress of interventions employed to meet the aspirations of the people, and for general M & E have been derived from what the people stated were their requirements and needs. The indicators will be improved upon in terms of their smartness when more information is obtained through the implementation of other Work Packages of the project.

7 GENERAL CONCLUSIONS

The CIRAWA project started in the 8 islands/districts/zones/regions with stakeholder engagement in which over 1,500 farmers and over 500 other stakeholders were sensitized on the importance of agroecology through visits to communities in the areas and other activities. The multi-actor approach was also used to gain a good understanding of the requirements and needs of the people. FGDs, KIIs, in-depth household surveys and other ways were used to obtain the information from men, women, and youth farmers as well as other stakeholders. The diverse requirements and needs of the farmers and community members of the 8 chosen CIRAWA regions in the four countries have been documented. The main requirements in almost all areas are improvements in soil fertility (with emphasis on use of compost and other bio-fertilizers), water availability and management, appropriate mechanization, access to markets, soil conservation measures, better housing for livestock and provision of feed all year round, access to production resources by women and youth, and others. Some SMART indicators have been teased out of the farmers' and communities' stated requirements and needs for the purpose of using them to assess, monitor and evaluate the progress of interventions that will be employed to address the stated requirements and needs of the people. The indicators will continue to be "smartened" as more field activities are undertaken.

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